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**“STRATEGIC CULTURAL CHANGE: A REAL WORLD APPLICATION EXAMPLE
IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR”**

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INTRODUCTION

The General Secretariat for Public Revenue of the Hellenic Economic Ministry is the national authority with the responsibility for the collection of tax and custom revenues for the Greek State.

The goal of our project is to create the framework for bringing about strategic culture change in the operations of the General Secretariat for Public Revenue (GSPR).

To assist in transforming the organization from a traditional hierarchical organization which is internally focused on its own needs (of revenue collection), characterized by a strict vertical chain of command to an agile horizontal process driven organization characterized by its versatility and ability to pre-react to the challenges of the changing external environment and the needs of its internal “customers” (employees) and external “customers” (taxpayers & society), through the empowering of its personnel (able people) and achieving process excellence (agile processes).

BACKGROUND – PROJECT JUSTIFICATION & NEED

The strategic focus of the GSPR has been on the development and utilization of its “traditional” business tools, heavily weighted on enforcement and on improving enforcement and on achieving quantitative goals. Limited awareness and consequently interest and recourses are directed toward quality of services, total quality and external/internal satisfaction related goals. This has not been only a result of the internal logic of the organization but also of the external environment which has encouraged, supported and exerted pressure for higher revenue collection. The economic crisis has intensified this process, as budget related strains and the need to maximize revenue have become of paramount importance. As a result various externally or internally ad hoc / “quick win” improvements have been undertaken as well as a systematic restructuring plan which have lead to mixed results. These changes have been undertaken with a top down approach without the involvement of the “people” base of the organization, who are faced with the pressure of dealing with high taxpayer

dissatisfaction, working within a structure which is changing beyond their understanding and thus increasing their dissatisfaction and lack of commitment to these changes.

The limitations of this approach have become increasingly obvious and solutions are considered in order to bring about inclusion of the personnel in order to achieve the strategic goals of the GSPR. This project has been set up as a response to this lack of qualitative human focus in order to address this issue and to find solutions leading to the development of a quality strategy for the organization.

THEORETICAL MODEL UTILIZED

According to **Kuipers & Higgs¹** literature review for public organizations change findings and references: **“Birkland (2011) used the *Input, Process, Output and Outcome* concepts to study policy processes in public sector. Applying these concepts to *organisational change*, we view change outcomes as substantive results (positive or negative) which differ from outputs. Processes are the ways in which the outputs are obtained. Outputs are often easier to measure than Outcomes. In particular, the reform literature has a profound tradition of sector and even cross-national comparisons of sectoral changes (e.g. Kuhlman 2010). Unfortunately, such comparisons pay little or no attention to the management of change processes *within the organisations* subject to these “sectoral perspective” of Change”**

In our project we consider Culture (Employees’ Engagement Culture), Accountability (Leadership Accountability) and Internal Process (Employee Centric Interoperability) as Systemic Enablers. We also consider Process Effectiveness (Internal Customer Effectiveness), measured by *Employee Satisfaction Surveys*. Finally we consider *Balanced Results* as Outcome, measured by *Taxpayers Satisfaction Surveys*. We consider quick wins in *Employees’ Culture Change* as the most important Critical Success Factor in order to manage Strategic Change in GSPR.

The project is based on the international experience concerning operational excellence. According to international approach to excellence and in order to achieve operational excellence in an organization,

¹ Kuipers, B.S., Higgs, M.J., Kickert, W.J.M., Tummens, L.G., Grandia, J., Van der Voet, J., ” The management of change in public organisations: «A literature review. Public Administration, UK,2014”

a three tier model approach should be followed on the following three excellence cycles with regard to public organization activities:

- T1. Internal core level: **Process** excellence (via BPM – business process mapping & BPR – business process re-engineering & corresponding process efficiency + effectiveness measurements KPIs – key performance indicators). [“AGILE PROCESS” STRATEGY]
- T2. Intermediate level: Organizational **culture change** for excellence (training on operational leadership & employee talent and personal development in order to develop a critical mass of human talent – “change agents” to empower and lead the organization turnaround management initiatives rollout). [“ABLE PEOPLE” STRATEGY]
- T3. Top level: Leadership **Accountability** (with regard to the successful achievement of mission, vision, social responsibility related strategic goals by the high–level leadership of the organization). [“ABLE PEOPLE” STRATEGY]

METHODOLOGY – PROJECT ROLLOUT – DELIVERABLES

Initial phase: Setting Benchmarks, disseminating operational excellence (mid 2014 till mid 2015).

A voluntary **work team** has been set up, composed of officials serving in different areas, with different competencies within the GSPR, in order to integrate operational excellence within the organization. As the need arose a larger pool of experts were utilized for specific projects, originating from within but also outside the organization.

As a first step in the process, **setting benchmarks** and **training in basic principles of operation excellence** were selected as the work team efforts and focus for the first year (mid 2014 till mid 2015), on the basis of the three levels approach (T1, T2 & T3) accomplishing three major and mile stone project deliverables (D1, D2 & D3):

D1.1 The design and execution of the first Employee Diagnostic Operational Survey: the purpose was to develop a Survey as a diagnostic tool in order to locate areas of major problems which are

characterized by a high level of employee dissatisfaction; to detect areas where improvements are required; to be used as a benchmark in order to measure effect of changes in operations on employee satisfaction level and the effectiveness of the implementation of the strategic plan, in comparison to subsequent similar surveys. The survey had as its target audience the total personnel of the GSPR (approx. 11000 employees), between 92% to 96% of personnel (of the 4 General Directorates) responded. The Survey was undertaken in-house, with no additional costs as employees with a statistical background as well as members of the group undertook the analysis and prepared the study document deliverable, at no cost to the GSPR.

D1.2 Standardization of Core end-to-end Processes: The team provides technical and scientific support to the General Directorates through the Gen. Directorate for Electronic Governance & Human Resources Mgmt for the task of mapping core business processes by taking full advantage of open-source Bizagi Process Modeler BPM-BPR toolkit. At this stage 1st level mapping for about 5 core procedures per department have been completed.

D2.1 Certified Training program in operational excellence: A strategic training program was implemented targeting officials at all levels of the organization and taking under consideration geographic distribution. Purpose of the trainings is to disseminate the concepts' of operational excellence throughout the organization and the preparation of qualified individuals for the role-out of the initial excellence cells, which will be assigned to carry out targeted tasks bringing improvements and change in specific areas. By the end of 2015 more than 450 officials, were trained under 2 certified programs, a standard program and/or an innovation workshop (in cooperation with the National Center for Public Governance - EKDDA).

D.2.2 Development and certification of the GSPR OpEx training programs syllabus: Two program syllabuses (on effective strategic change implementation methodology) were developed and certified, authored by the trainers, with significant input by the trainees (employee participation).

D.2.3 Training manual: The training specialists have developed a tailored made for the GSPR, complete-detailed training manual, (with the support of the National Center for Public Governance and with financial support of the EU through the ESPA program).

D3. OpEx multi-stakeholder engagement plan: A proposed action plan for the future escalation of the project including both a short term (next two year – current business planning orientation) as well as long term (5 years strategic planning orientation) was officially submitted to the SecGen in late 2015 by the OpEx Work Team, (40 pg proposal which correlates proposed actions with segmented findings of the survey in according to OpEx strategic framework logic levels and project deliverables).

Current phase: OpEx Incubator Cells – Innovative change projects (late 2015 and continuing).

Fourteen sub-groups (**OpEx incubator cells**) were created in accordance to the engagement plan. Two member of the initial central OpEx Work Team, volunteered to lead each cell (leader and his substitute) and the approx. 450 OpEx trained-certified officials who underwent the operational excellence program were invited to volunteer to join a cell. Each cell undertook to examine and propose novel ideas for change in its respective field (core business areas of the GSPR). 14 project proposals have been analyzed and developed by the cells of which 4 have been selected for future development and adoption into the organization, focusing on increasing overall revenue collection effectiveness.

Future activities under examination.

- In order to support the cells and as a method of increasing the participation and inclusion, the development of an operational **excellence network** for the promotion of OpEx and as an open

electronic forum for discussion and detection of innovative initiatives, which could materialize in projects to be developed by spinoff cells.

- **Awards** for best practices or innovative ideas of employees. Alternative scenarios in this direction are under examination by the OpEx Work Team.
- A **Coaching & Mentoring Initiative** is under examination, following the first positive cultural change impact of OpEx training, both as a finding and a consequence of the diagnostic survey (ad hoc leadership development to manage change under HR 360 evaluation standards).
- Currently the preparation has started for the repetition of the GSPR **Employee Diagnostic Operational Survey**. (planned for summer 2016); the analysis will include the data of the first survey for benchmarking. In addition the team is to expand its activities concerning surveys in the future, by developing and undertaking surveys focusing on measuring satisfaction of specific categories of employees, taxpayers and society (multi-stakeholder governance systemic approach – 2nd illustration), through questionnaires which most probably will be circulated through the use of electronic survey tools to targeted audiences (use of crowd sourcing tools are under examination). Long term proposed goal is firstly, to integrate the results into the planning and mgmt process and following this, to integrate it into program assessment and individual business unit performance evaluation.
- In parallel the team has proposed to consider the best methodology for the systematic collection & analysis of **customer complaints** and **satisfaction** feedback **trends**, with the goal to integrate this feedback into performance targets and performance measurements and overall as a tool which could become part of the business plan of the organization, moving the organization from reaction to prevention. First stage of this project expansion will be to set up various mechanisms for complaint collection and analysis (e.g. geo-spatial drill down analysis) for resolving operational issues as soon as they appear.

CONCLUSION

Under the difficult economic conditions faced by Greece and the considerable pressure placed on the GSPR for immediate quantitative results, actions can still be undertaken, with the purpose of transforming problems into opportunities in order to bring about meaningful structural change through motivation of the internal strengths (abilities-knowhow) of the people/base of the organization. The primary resources allocated by the GSPR were the allocation of employee time to be trained, certified and primarily the freedom/empowerment given to self-motivated, *engaged employees* to work creatively and unconstrained on a voluntary base to bring about innovative change in the organization.

The primary lesson of the project so far, is that by looking inwards large public organizations can find the willingness and ability in its own workforce to lead organizational change, limiting thus institutional resistance which characterizes top-down change initiatives.

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